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Title: Evaluation of Boolean operations between free-form solids using Extended Simplicial Chains and PN triangles

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Abstract: This paper presents a method to evaluate Boolean operations between free-form solids modeled using Extended Simplicial Chains (ESCs). The ESC model is a formal system to represent not only the boundary, but also the volume of free-form solids, that allows the development of simple and robust algorithms. In this implementation of the ESC model, the free-form solids and the results of the operations are bounded by PN triangles and represented by ESCs, and the surface intersection and trimming are computed using adaptive subdivision of the patches and a point in solid test specifically designed for ESCs.

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43 1 Introduction 44

45 In 1977, Requicha et al. published the basics of the
46 Constructive Solid Geometry system (CSG) [35], where
47 solid models are built by combining simpler models
48 (primitives) using Boolean operations. Since then, eval-
49 uation of Boolean operations has become an impor-
50 tant topic in Solid Modeling, as many applications like
51 CAD/CAM, representation of organic shapes, surgical
52 simulation, etcetera, depend on a reliable way of com-
53 puting the boundary of the solids modeled.

54 Dealing with free-form solids (i.e. solids with curved
55 boundaries) makes the evaluation of Boolean operations
56 especially difficult, as it implies computing the inter-
57 sections between curved surfaces that can be defined
58 using algebraic or (more frequently) parametric forms.
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An alternative option is the visualization of CSG solids
without computing the boundary of the results [34, 14].

However, there exist applications that necessarily de-
pend on the computation of the boundary of the re-
sult of CSG-modeled solids. Therefore, evaluation of
Boolean operations between free-form solid primitives
is still an open issue in the field of Computer Graphics.

Typically, surfaces of free-form solids are modeled as
a set of patches. Obtaining the result of a Boolean oper-
ation between free-form solids modeled in this way is a
complex task that can be decomposed into several steps.
The first step in this process consists of computing the
intersections amid the patches from the solids. This is a
well-known problem that has been widely studied [32];
approaches to solve this problem include curve trac-
ing [29, 23], curve marching [33], subdivision methods
[2, 32], numerical methods [16, 13] and hardware-based
methods [20]. Some of these methods can produce a
faulty set of curves; therefore, some works try to ensure
that the topology of the result is correct [41, 15].

The second step consists of the trimming of the sur-
face patches that bound the solids using the intersec-
tion curves as trimming curves. This topic has also been
covered in many papers, and solutions have been pre-
sented for different kind of surfaces, including implicit
[31], parametric [44, 6] or subdivision surfaces [26].

Finally, the third step is the selection of the trimmed
patches that form the boundary of the result, depending
on the operation. In this step, an efficient and robust
method to determine which patches must be selected
and which ones have to be discarded is necessary. Dif-
ferent strategies have been proposed to address the full
process of evaluation of Boolean operations with free-
form solids: approximate solutions can be obtained by
working with the control point nets of the solids [25, 4];
application of combinations of algebraic and numerical
methods to compute the intersection and trimming of
patches [22, 21]; lazy arithmetic has also been used in or-

der to reduce the numerical instability of some of these proposals [19,18]. Although most of the work that has been done up to now is based on parametric and subdivision surfaces, there are also interesting references that make use of algebraic surface patches [3].

The solutions mentioned above consider free-form solids as modelled in a B-Rep-like way. In this work we present a method to evaluate Boolean operations between free-form solids modelled using *Extended Simplicial Chains* (ESCs) as the underlying data model. The ESC model [38,9] is a solid representation system that considers each solid as the result of the combination of the volumes from a series of cells that are not required to be disjoint and can be obtained straightforwardly. Some advantages of the ESC model are:

- It is a formal model, with well-defined components and operations.
- It allows the development of simple, robust and reliable algorithms, with very few special cases that can be easily detected and solved [10,8].
- It represents not only the boundary, but also the volume of the solid, in a better way than other solid modeling data structures like octrees.

Up to now, the ESC model had been used to represent and visualize non-evaluated Boolean operations [37,11]. In this work the ESC model is applied to the evaluation of Boolean operations between solids bounded by PN triangles as an example of parametric surface patch.

The following sections are organized as follows: section 2.1 summarizes the basics of PN triangles; section 2.2 presents a brief overview of the ESC model; an outline of the algorithms for the intersection and trimming of PN triangles is given in section 3; section 4 describes how the trimmed patches are stitched together in the resulting solid, and finally, sections 5 and 6 discuss the results obtained and present our conclusions.

2 Background

2.1 PN triangles

Triangular Bézier patches (TBPs) are cited [5] as the first extension of the Bézier curves to surfaces, and as a more natural generalization than tensor product patches are. As with polygons, it is easier to model a surface with triangular elements than with square ones [5]. PN triangles are a special case of TBP developed by ATI [1,42]; due to their simplicity, these patches can be easily processed using the GPU [39]. Here we consider free-form solids as bounded by a set of PN triangles.

PN triangles are cubic TBPs defined by a triangular control point net with 10 points. Each control point is named b_{ijk} , with $i \geq 0$, $j \geq 0$, $k \geq 0$, and $i + j + k = 3$. The parametric domain is triangular, having

Fig. 1 Parametric domain and control points of a PN triangle

Fig. 2 PN triangle

three parameters, u , v and w , that take value from the continuous interval $[0, 1]$; the sum $u + v + w$ always equals 1.0. Figure 1 shows the domain and location of the control points for a PN triangle.

Points on the surface can be calculated using the Bernstein polynomials, given by:

$$B_{i,j,k}^3(u,v,w) = \frac{3!}{i! \cdot j! \cdot k!} \cdot u^i \cdot v^j \cdot w^k; \quad (1)$$

Calling λ the 3-tuple (i, j, k) and τ the 3-tuple (u, v, w) , we obtain the expression for a PN triangle:

$$b^3(\tau) = \sum_{|\lambda|=3} b_\lambda \cdot B_\lambda^3(\tau); \quad (2)$$

$|\lambda| = 3$ stands for all the 3-tuples (i, j, k) which satisfy $i + j + k = 3$. In this paper, we will call the triangle determined by the control points b_{300} , b_{030} and b_{003} the *base triangle* of the PN triangle (in red in Figure 2).

Subdivision is an important feature that is intensively used in our work. Seidel [40] describes this process. Moreover, Li et al. [24] proposed a method to compute how many times a TBP should be subdivided for a given precision value; however, this method occasionally suffers from numerical instability.

2.2 The Extended Simplicial Chain model

The Extended Simplicial Chain (ESC) model [38,9] is a mathematical model to represent free-form solids that extends the concept of Simplicial Chain presented in [7]. It considers each solid to be modeled by an ESC defined as:

$$\delta = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i \cdot E_i \quad (3)$$

Fig. 3 Left: model and origin of an ESC. Right: a positive ($OV_1V_2V_3$, in red) and a negative ($OV_5V_7V_8$, in blue) original simplices drawn over a triangulation of the model

where α_i are integer coefficients, and E_i are *extended cells*. An extended cell can be one of the following:

- An *original simplex*. An original d -dimensional simplex is defined as the convex hull of $d+1$ linearly independent points, one of which is shared with all the other simplices in the ESC, and is called the *origin* of the chain; any point of the Euclidean space can be taken as origin of an ESC. Regarding three dimensional original simplices, the three vertices that differ from the origin of the chain are the vertices of a triangle from a polyhedral model that approximates the boundary of the solid. Depending on the orientation of the triangle with respect to the origin of the chain, an original simplex can have positive or negative volume (Figure 3).
- A *free-form cell*. A d -dimensional free-form cell (ffc) is a set of points in \mathbb{R}^d , enclosed by a free-form element of topological dimension $(d-1)$ and one or more planar elements of topological dimension $(d-1)$ that verifies:
 1. It is a closed and connected set in \mathbb{R}^d .
 2. Every point lies on the same connected component (sign-invariant) with regard to the implicit equation of the free-form element, except the ones on the boundary of the cell.
 3. The points shared by a number of bounding elements greater than or equal to the dimension of the cell belong to the free-form element too.

Free-form element stands for a non-planar geometric entity in \mathbb{R}^d , like a curve in 2D or a surface in 3D, while *planar element* stands for a planar geometric entity in \mathbb{R}^d , like a line in 2D or a plane in 3D.

An extended study on the definition and the conditions above is available in the references [38,9].

Applying the above definition, a three dimensional free-form cell is considered in this work as the set of points bounded by a set of planes and a small set of PN triangles. One of the PN triangles is the *main patch* of the ffc, while the set of planes includes the plane that contains the base triangle of the main patch, and three more planes, each one containing one edge of the same base triangle. Only in those cases where there are gaps between the side planes of the ffc and the main patch (e.g. when the control points from the border of the main patch are not coplanar), the set of PN triangles

Fig. 4 Left: bounding elements of a 3-dimensional ffc (the side planes are drawn as four-sided polygons; the plane containing the base triangle is not drawn). Right: volume of the same ffc

include additional patches to the main patch [10]. Figure 4 shows an instance of a 3-dimensional ffc.

Unlike other decomposition-based models [36,43], a major advantage of the ESC model is that the extended cells do not need to be disjoint; therefore the ESC for a given solid can be built easily.

The starting point to build an ESC can be an initial triangulation that approximates the boundary of the solid. Then an interpolation scheme is applied in order to build the patches that form the boundary of the solid [42], and finally each triangle determines an original simplex, and one ffc is created for each patch [10]. If the starting point of the ESC building process is a B-Rep consisting of a set of PN triangles, the simplices are built from the base triangles of the patches.

The origin of an ESC can be any point in the Euclidean space, either inside or outside the solid. Moreover, it is not necessary for a set of ESCs that are going to be combined in a boolean operation to share the same origin. Should the origin is in a position that produces degenerate original simplices (i.e. zero volume simplices), they would be treated in the same way that the other ones; it is only necessary to be aware of their features when performing computations like point in simplex test. Anyway, this is a very unlikely situation, and it can be solved just by displacing the origin of the ESC to a different position.

Each extended cell has an associated sign, depending on its orientation with respect to the solid. Positive cells add their volume to the solid, while negative cells subtract their volume from the solid. We consider the coefficient α_i for each cell E_i equal to its sign.

Situations like the one shown in Figure 5 are handled by considering two ffc that share the same bounding elements: the first ffc is positive, and consists of the set of points that is located in the positive half-space defined by the plane that contains the base triangle; the second one is negative, and consists of the set of points that is located in the negative half-space defined by the plane that contains the base triangle.

For any given point, the *function associated with an ESC* is an integer-valued function defined as the sum of the coefficients associated with the extended cells of

Fig. 5 A patch intersecting its base triangle causes the appearance of two fcs: a positive one (in green) and a negative one (in blue)

the ESC that contain the point:

$$f_{\delta} : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$$

$$f_{\delta}(\mathbf{Q}) = \sum_{\mathbf{Q} \in E_i} \alpha_i \quad (4)$$

Using this function, the *free-form solid associated with an ESC* is defined as the set of all the points \mathbf{Q} that verifies:

$$FF_{\delta} = \{\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^3 / f_{\delta}(\mathbf{Q}) \neq 0\} \quad (5)$$

Special cases appear when a point is on a bounding element shared by two or more extended cells. In order to easily handle these situations, regularization [35] is applied to the ESC model as follows [38]: let p and n be the maximum and the minimum of the values of f_{δ} in an arbitrarily small neighborhood of a point \mathbf{Q} :

$$p = \max\{f_{\delta}(\mathbf{Q}') \mid \forall \mathbf{Q}' \in N_{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{Q})\}$$

$$n = \min\{f_{\delta}(\mathbf{Q}') \mid \forall \mathbf{Q}' \in N_{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{Q})\} \quad (6)$$

The *regular function associated with an ESC* δ is:

$$f_{\delta}^* : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$$

$$f_{\delta}^*(\mathbf{Q}) = 0 \quad \text{if } \mathbf{Q} \notin \text{closure}(\text{interior}(FF_{\delta}))$$

$$f_{\delta}^*(\mathbf{Q}) = p \quad \text{if } p > 0$$

$$f_{\delta}^*(\mathbf{Q}) = n \quad \text{otherwise} \quad (7)$$

In order to simplify the operations, *normal ESCs* are always considered. A *normal ESC* is defined as the one that verifies that:

$$f_{\delta}^*(\mathbf{Q}) = 1, \quad \forall \mathbf{Q} \in FF_{\delta} \quad (8)$$

An algorithm to compute the point in solid test can be easily implemented using f_{δ} : just compute the inclusion test individually for each cell of the ESC, add the results and compare the sum with 1 [10]. Testing the inclusion of a point in a simplex is easy: simply check its barycentric coordinates with respect to the simplex vertices. To study the inclusion of a point in a ffc, an algorithm based on the Jordan curve theorem [17] was implemented successfully due to the structural simplicity of the ffc, because the ray-plane intersection is easily computed, and only a few ray-patch intersection test are necessary (one per patch that forms the

Fig. 6 Example of parametric subdivision. Two levels of the hierarchy are shown with one subdivision per level

free-form element that bounds the ffc). As most of the volume of the solids is represented just by simplices, the situations where the inclusion of a point in a ffc has to be tested are very few, and therefore the average computational cost of the point in solid test algorithm is very low [10]. This algorithm also allows us to easily build other standard volumetric representations, like voxel enumeration, that can be used for specific purposes.

Boolean operations can also be expressed as operations with ESCs [38,9]. However, here we apply a simplification technique consisting of evaluating the boundary of the result using the inclusion test developed for ESCs, and then creating the new ESC for the result as explained before [37].

3 PN triangles intersection and trimming

To evaluate the result of a Boolean operation between free-form solids, it is necessary to compute the intersection and trimming of their surfaces. As we consider here the solids bounded by PN triangles, we need robust and effective algorithms to handle these problems.

Algorithms to perform these tasks were presented in [12]. These algorithms use a hierarchical data structure, also used to compute the point in solid test and to visualize the solids using ray casting [10,8]. Each PN triangle has an associated hierarchy with n levels, and each node in a level stores m subpatches (Figure 6). The total amount of subpatches at the deepest level of the hierarchy for a PN triangle is $(m+1)^{2n}$. The values of m and n can be fixed, or can be computed by applying the algorithm proposed in [24].

3.1 Computing the intersection

The algorithm to compute the intersection of PN triangles uses the hierarchy intensively. The intersection curve is computed as a piecewise linear sequence of segments obtained by intersecting the base triangles of the subpatches in the leaf nodes of the hierarchy [28]. The

Fig. 7 Subdivisions used to compute the intersection between two PN triangles

Fig. 8 Segments that are stored separately (in red)

Fig. 9 Reorientation of connected components

intersection is computed only in those cases where the subpatches are prone to intersect, after a series of intersection tests among the bounding boxes of the nodes of the hierarchies from the patches (Figure 7).

Segments obtained from each triangle-triangle intersection are binned into candidate connected components. Segments that cause the appearance of loops and bifurcations are stored separately (Figure 8), and candidate components that are joined together by a new segment are reoriented if necessary (Figure 9). Segments are studied and stored as they are computed. Therefore, the choice of the red segments in the figures depends only on the moment they are computed, the last one being the one that is stored separately.

In the next stage, the candidate components and the segments separately stored are processed to obtain simple connected components, either closed or open. The behaviour of the patches is quite predictable, due to their low degree, and the special cases are reduced to a minimum [12]. The segments are added one by one to the candidate components; when the addition of a segment causes a closed loop, it is cut out and stored as a final closed component. The result of the process is a set of either closed or open connected components.

3.2 Patch trimming

Once the intersection curves are computed, the next step is the trimming of the patches that are intersected, depending on the operation. The patch trimming algo-

Fig. 10 Steps of the PN triangle trimming algorithm

rithm presented here also deals with the levels of detail hierarchy [12]. Figure 10 illustrates the steps:

1. Compute the intersection curves between the patch to be trimmed and the bounding elements of the trimming solid (Figure 10.a).
2. Combine the obtained intersection curves with the boundaries of the patch in a set of *temporary boundaries* (Figure 10.b). This includes finding the intersection points among the curves and dividing them into simple and connected components.
3. Tessellate the parametric domain of the subpatches whose base triangles were used to compute the intersection curves [30]. Subdivide the subpatches and their base triangles according to this tessellation (Figure 10.c).
4. Delete the subpatches that are inside the trimming solid, using a point inclusion test [10] (Figure 10.d).
5. Delete the temporary boundaries that are inside the trimming solid, using a point inclusion test [10] (Figure 10.e).
6. Establish the new boundaries (Figure 10.f).

In step 3 of the trimming process, the barycentric coordinates of the points from the piecewise linear intersection curve with respect to the base triangles of the subpatches are used to tessellate their parametric domains. This causes an accuracy error, whose magnitude depends on the depth and width of the levels of detail hierarchy, that has to be handled later. At the same time, we use the piecewise linear intersection curve to trim and tessellate the base triangles of the subpatches.

Fig. 11 PN triangles for the result of a Boolean operation. Left: using hierarchies with one level and one subdivision per level. Right: using two levels and three subdivisions per level

Fig. 12 Results obtained applying the first approach to correct the PN triangles from the trimming operation

During the trimming operation, information about deleted subpatches is propagated upwards in the hierarchy; the nodes whose children have been deleted previously are then trimmed. As a result, the trimmed patch is represented by a set of simple PN triangles.

4 Assembling the result

The boundary of the result of a Boolean operation between free-form solids modeled using ESCs as described above is a set of PN triangles chosen according to the operation. Using the algorithm explained before to trim the patches results in a more or less disconnected boundary, depending on the level of detail used when doing the trim, as it is based on the barycentric coordinates of the intersection between the base triangles of the subpatches (Figure 11). However, the set of triangles underneath the trimming operation that was also computed by trimming and tessellating the base triangles of the subpatches is a correct and closed triangle mesh that approximates the boundary of the solid.

It is then necessary to correct the PN triangles from the trimming operation to achieve a closed boundary for the resulting solid. Some works have been published on this topic, using displacement maps to modify the trimmed surfaces [41]. Instead of that, we have studied and tested several simpler heuristics to modify the surfaces, taking advantage of the low degree of the patches:

- The first approach is straightforward: as the triangulation obtained from the trimming process is topologically correct, use this triangulation as an approximation to the surface of the new solid, and apply an interpolation scheme to get a new set of PN triangles [42]. Figure 12 shows some results.

Fig. 13 Steps for the second approach to correct the PN triangles from the trimming operation

Fig. 14 Result obtained applying the second approach to correct the PN triangles from Figure 11

- The second approach is a hole capping algorithm. Figure 13 illustrates its steps:
 1. Replace the triangle vertices with the corresponding corners of the PN triangles where they do not match (Figure 13.b). As a result, a gap appears.
 2. Create two new triangles to fill the gap that has appeared (Figure 13.c).
 3. Create two new PN triangles based on the triangles from the previous step to close the boundary of the solid (Figure 13.d), using the same interpolation scheme that was applied before [42].
 The results obtained with this method are better than with the first approach, as shown in Figure 14.
- The third approach consists of a joint modification of the control points from the boundaries of the PN triangles that do not match and of the vertices of the triangles (Figure 15):
 1. The corners of the PN triangles that should meet are replaced by their average (Figs. 15.b and 15.c).
 2. Then, the inner control points of the boundary are replaced by averaging them with the corresponding points from the neighbouring PN triangles (Figs. 15.d and 15.e).

Fig. 15 Steps for the third approach to correct the PN triangles from the trimming operation

Fig. 16 Result obtained applying the third approach to correct the PN triangles from Figure 11

3. Finally, the vertices of the triangles are replaced with the new corners of the corresponding PN triangles (Figs. 15.f).

This solution produces the best visual results, as Figure 16 shows.

The first two approaches have significant shortcomings: the first one results in a general smoothing of the solid, see Figure 12; the second approach presented several special cases (like patches rotated with respect to its neighbours) that are difficult to detect and handle. The third approach works best for our purposes, and has been selected as the method to correct the PN triangles.

Once a topologically correct set of patches have been obtained, the new simplified ESC that represents the result of the Boolean operation can be directly computed. There are two possible ways to do this:

- The first approach consists of creating a simplex and a ffc for each patch or subpatch whose descendants have not been deleted. The base triangles of the patches or subpatches that have been used will form the new triangle mesh that approximates the boundary of the solid (see Figure 17 up). This method produces an optimized number of extended cells. However, it implies a complex traversal of the levels of detail hierarchy, and it is necessary to subdivide the patches whose neighbours have been trimmed in order to avoid cracks in the triangulation [27].
- The second method consists of using the subpatches at the leaf nodes of the levels of detail hierarchy of each PN triangle. A simplex and a ffc are built for each subpatch stored at a leaf node. The base triangles of the subpatches will form the new triangle mesh that approximates the boundary of the solid.

Fig. 17 Up: first method to build the ESC. Simplices and patches considered to build the fcs after the trimming process for a non-trimmed PN triangle (left) and a trimmed PN triangle (right). Down: alternative method to build the ESC, using all the subpatches stored at the leaf nodes of the hierarchies

Table 1 Information about the models used in the tests

Model	Patches	Triangle equivalence ($n = 2, m = 3$)
Stomach	534	136704
Hand	768	196608
Liver	274	70144
Mushroom	448	114688

Figure 17 down shows the set of simplices that is obtained from a trimmed and a non-trimmed PN triangle using this method. As these subpatches are also PN triangles, the cell creation process is straightforward, and a complete and correct ESC is obtained. This method has been implemented and successfully tested (see results in Figs. 18 to 20).

The first method can produce an ESC with less extended cells in those cases where the trimming is small and reduced to a little portion of the solids. Otherwise, it implies an unnecessarily complex process compared to its advantages.

5 Results

The algorithms have been implemented in C++ and successfully tested in a Intel[®] Core[™] 2 Quad 2.4 GHz PC with 4 GB of RAM memory. Although it is a multi-core architecture, the algorithms were tested with only one core. Table 1 shows the number of PN triangles that bound the models used in our tests. Depending on the parameters used to build the levels of detail hierarchies for the PN triangles, the equivalent polyhedral meshes can contain several thousand triangles; as an example, Table 1 shows the equivalence for $n = 2$ and $m = 3$.

Figs. 18 to 20 have been obtained using the techniques described above to trim and correct the PN triangles. After that, new ESCs have been built using the second proposed method to obtain ESCs. Figures 21 and 22 show two examples of more complex CSG mod-

Table 2 Information from Figs. 18 to 22

Figure	B-Rep evaluation	Boundary correction	ESC creation	Number of calls to patch-patch intersection	Number of calls to triangle-triangle intersection	Number of segments
18	3.33 sec.	0.005 sec.	0.14 sec.	619014	62144	1294
19	2.64 sec.	0.005 sec.	0.13 sec.	551808	43008	812
20	3.02 sec.	0.01 sec.	0.24 sec.	263698	903680	1944
21	2.8 sec.	0.02 sec.	0.6 sec.	139026	84000	1214
22	1.65 sec.	0.01 sec.	0.33 sec.	147842	55360	650

Fig. 22 A CSG solid and the intermediate steps of its modeling process

result is computed using the ESC model as the underlying solid representation.

The application of the ESC model to free-form solids bounded with PN triangles [9, 10] has been summarized, as well as the algorithms to intersect and trim these kind of patches [12] using the point in solid test for free-form solids presented in [10]. Taking this previous work as starting point, the evaluation of the boundary, including accuracy errors correction and the building of an ESC for the result of a Boolean operation between two free-form solids has been presented. The new ESC does not differ in its structure from the chains of the original solids, and then it can be used in successive

operations. The ESC system is therefore a closed and useful formal model to handle free-form solids in a simple way. Moreover, algorithms that work on ESCs can be quite easily parallelized.

The possibility of evaluating boolean operations makes the ESC model suitable for applications like virtual surgery and sculpting, representation of organic shapes or CAD applications.

A still open issue is the representation of volumetric properties; as the Extended Simplicial Chain model is a volume representation, it is possible to include the ability to represent volumetric properties. This would make the model very suitable for the representation of heterogeneous solids.

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